

12th International Manikin and Modelling Meeting
29-31 August 2018, St. Gallen, Switzerland

A multi-sector cylinder for ISO 18640-1, specially designed for studying clothing sweat management, working in hot climates and dynamic physiological control

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1404493

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Introduction

In spite of having multiple sectors, heated sweating thermal manikins have been primarily designed for standard measurements for which a single constant temperature is set over the whole body surface. Nevertheless, in an attempt to simulate the true thermal response of the human, such manikins have increasingly being controlled by thermo-physiological models of the human. Due to deficiencies in manikin design, such control is limited in its application and accuracy [1].

Using a cylinder to represent thermally the torso of the human body is not new [2] [3]. Advantages over manikins with anatomical body forms are:

- a) single and multiple textile layers can be assessed without the need to construct clothing, simply by rapping them around the cylinder, with or without air gaps. Air gaps, if present, can have a well-defined geometry using a spacer textile or frame.
- b) such a cylindrical system is relatively inexpensive to produce and maintain

A single-sector cylinder Torso is now being established as an international standard (ISO 18640-1) [4]. However, varying wind velocities around the cylinder (as seen in figure 1) cause varying heat fluxes to result. Furthermore, different clothing layers are worn over the pelvic, abdominal and thoracic regions of the torso. Sweat distribution can differ significantly over different regions of the torso [5]. Thus a multi-sector torso system, subdivided axially and radially, with thermally independent and dynamically responsive sectors, is desirable for more detailed measurement of local heat flux and accurate simulation of the human thermal response.

Advanced design

An advanced multi-sector cylinder, called *iSimU*, is presented and has been developed to meet the above challenges by Humanikin GmbH in collaboration with lululemon and the Apparel Innovation Centre in Calgary, Canada. The 12-sector version of the *iSimU* system, shown in figure 2, has the following features:

- i) Conformity with ISO 18640 part 1
- ii) The ISO 18640 measurement area is divided into three identical sub-cylinders, representing thorax, abdomen and pelvic areas of the torso enabling overlapping upper and lower body clothing to be measured practically.
- iii) Each of these three sub-cylinders are quartered giving front, back and side sectors
- iv) Each of the resulting twelve sectors has the following layers:
 - a. A temperature sensor covering the surface
 - b. A heat flux sensor layer to determine the integral surface heat flux
 - c. An integrated heating layer
 - d. An integrated cooling layer
 - e. An array of digital moisture sensors embedded in the sector surface

The moisture sensors are used to measure the wicking/spread of moisture from each of the 48 sweating outlets horizontally and vertically in the textile layer directly in contact with the surface of the *iSimU*.

Figure 1 Flow of 1 m/s from an aperture of 0.8m at a distance 1 m in front of the 30 cm ϕ cylinder using COMSOL Multiphysics with the heat transfer module. Wall separation is 1.5 m.

Figure 2 Schematic diagram showing the 12 central measurement sectors, with heated guards above and below.

Results and Conclusions

ISO standard and additional results of *iSimU* shall be presented for a range of climatic conditions. Initial focus is set on ensuring conformity to the above standard, simulating the relatively slow response of the Torso. Coupling *iSimU* to a thermo-physiological model is foreseen to take advantage of the dynamic sector response, with the front-back-2-side subdivision of each sub-cylinder corresponding to that of the model.

References

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